

A Novel Approach to Human Activity Recognition: Integrating Automated Machine Learning and Multimodal Fusion Mechanisms

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Abstract—The realm of computer vision has maintained a sustained interest in human activity recognition for an extended duration, given its myriad applications across diverse domains such as medicine, surveillance, entertainment, and human-computer interaction. This research introduces a sophisticated, expeditiously trainable, and adaptable system designed for human activity recognition. This system leverages an automated machine learning methodology grounded in Neural Architecture Search. The proposed approach integrates information from various channels within a 3D video, including RGB and depth data, skeletal information, and contextual objects. These data streams are independently processed through 2D convolutional neural networks. Subsequently, the outcomes of these networks are amalgamated into a consolidated array of class scores through fusion mechanisms characterized by computational efficiency and the extraction of meaningful information from the video. To validate the efficacy of the proposed system, extensive experimentation is conducted using three publicly available datasets. The experimental results demonstrate a notable level of accuracy across all evaluated datasets. These findings underscore the robust performance of the proposed system in the realm of human activity recognition. This research presents the amalgamation of 2D-3D CNN for Human Activity Recognition with Multi Model Fusion Mechanism.

Keywords—Human activity recognition, Skeletal data, Convolutional neural networks, Multimodal fusion

I. INTRODUCTION

Human Activity Recognition (HAR) constitutes a consequential sub-domain within computer vision, offering significant potential for enhancing the quality of life through the development of solutions that afford computers the capability to comprehend human behavior within diverse environments. This comprehension, in turn, empowers computational systems to proactively respond to varying situational contexts. This research introduces an innovative real-time framework for human activity recognition characterized by several salient features. Firstly, the employed fusion mechanisms hinge on elementary mathematical concepts, rendering them intuitive, computationally straightforward, and readily understandable. Secondly, the implemented methodology demonstrates efficacy through its precision and temporal efficiency. Thirdly, the expeditious trainability of the system is realized through the utilization of Google's Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) tools, incorporating robust Neural Architecture Search (NAS) and transfer learning techniques. Lastly, the framework's inherent modularity facilitates seamless customization, enabling adaptation to a spectrum of real-world applications. The proposed Human Activity Recognition (HAR) methodology integrates information from all channels within a 3D video, encompassing RGB and depth data, the human skeleton, and contextual objects. This amalgamation is facilitated through the implementation of three distinct fusion mechanisms: temporal, channel, and context. Initially, each data stream undergoes a process of "compression" into a 2D representation, constituting the temporal fusion mechanism. Subsequently, these compressed representations are input into specialized Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The choice of CNNs over conventional approaches, such as those reliant on hand-crafted features, is motivated by the established efficacy of CNNs in yielding state-of-the-art results for intricate activity recognition tasks [1]. Each CNN produces an array of likelihood scores reflecting the probability of specific activities. The next stage involves the amalgamation of these scores through a decision-making strategy, constituting the channel fusion mechanism. This strategic fusion serves to consolidate the outputs from individual CNNs into a comprehensive assessment of activity likelihoods. To further enhance accuracy, an additional layer of refinement is introduced through the consideration of contextual information. This is achieved by weighting the likelihood scores based on the identification of surrounding objects within the video, constituting the context fusion mechanism. This supplementary step aims to provide nuanced insights by incorporating the contextual relevance of identified objects in the overall activity recognition process. In essence, the proposed methodology employs a multi-stage fusion approach, encompassing temporal, channel, and context mechanisms, to synthesize information from diverse channels within the 3D video and achieve a refined and accurate representation of human activities. The underpinning theoretical framework of our proposed method is grounded in three key concepts. Firstly, we posit that a video, constituting an ordered sequence of frames, can be effectively compressed into a single image termed as a motion history image [2]. This conceptualization implies that the efficacy of activity recognition in videos can be distilled into the more tractable problem of image classification. Secondly, our approach aligns with the principle that aggregating multiple results, even if individually lacking high accuracy, is likely to converge towards a correct solution [3], [4]. Lastly, we subscribe to the notion that classifications performed on diverse data streams contribute meaningfully to overall accuracy when amalgamated with varying confidence coefficients [5], [6].

The primary objective of this paper is to empirically demonstrate the validity and utility of these theoretical underpinnings within the context of Human Activity Recognition (HAR). Through rigorous experimentation, we seek to substantiate the effectiveness of compressing videos into motion history images, the advantages of combining diverse results, and the utility of leveraging

classifications from different data streams with varying confidence coefficients. In doing so, we aim to contribute substantively to the body of knowledge on HAR methodologies. Furthermore, this paper serves the secondary purpose of augmenting the repository of public benchmarks specifically tailored for RGB-D video-based activity detection challenges. By introducing new benchmarks, we endeavor to foster advancements in the broader research community and provide a standardized evaluation framework for the systematic assessment of diverse HAR approaches utilizing RGB-D video data.

II. RELATED WORK

In their work presented in [7], the authors propose a composite system comprising two parallel Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) characterized by distinct inputs. A key aspect of their investigation involves exploring various mechanisms for temporal fusion within video sequences, aiming to enable the utilization of 2D CNNs as opposed to 3D CNNs. The two designated inputs are denoted as the fovea stream and the context stream, each designed to process different regions of the video frames. The fovea stream operates exclusively on the central portion of the frames, involving down-sampling the video frames to half of their original size. Conversely, the context stream extracts feature from low-resolution frames by cropping only the middle region of the video frames. Employing transfer learning in conjunction with this dual-stream architecture, the system achieves a performance score of 63.3% on the UCF-101 dataset [8]. However, the authors note that the temporal fusion model utilized in their approach demonstrates limited effectiveness in terms of accuracy when compared to straightforward classifications performed on individual video frames. The observed increment in accuracy is marginal, merely amounting to 1.6%. This observation leads to the inference that the employed CNN architecture may not be optimal for the task at hand. Consequently, it underscores the importance of further exploration and refinement of CNN architectures to enhance the temporal fusion aspect and subsequently improve overall system performance.

The pronounced efficiency advantage derived from the compression of videos into images, facilitated by a fusion mechanism, is underscored in [9]. In contrast to training a neural network directly on raw videos, the proposed methodology entails training on compressed video representations. This approach not only achieves notable accuracy, registering 94.9% on the UCF-101 dataset [10] and 70.2% on HMDB-41 [11] with optical flow but also exhibits heightened efficiency. Notably, it outperforms the Res3D (3D Residual ConvNet architecture) by being 4.6 times faster [12]. The outcomes demonstrated an accuracy of 91.3% on the first dataset and 58.4% on the second dataset. This substantiates the significance of fusion mechanisms within Human Activity Recognition (HAR) systems, elucidating the substantial speedup achieved when classifying images as opposed to processing entire videos. The findings underscore the practical implications of leveraging fusion mechanisms for enhanced efficiency in HAR, contributing valuable insights to the optimization of video processing methodologies.

In [13], an influential contribution is made with the introduction of a robust binary action descriptor tailored for depth sequences. This descriptor, grounded in τ tests, demonstrates commendable invariance to variations in scale, background, occlusion, viewpoint, and rotation. The method, validated through action recognition experiments on the MSRDailyActivity3D dataset [14], achieves a noteworthy accuracy of 95.62%. Noteworthy is the method's independence from skeleton information; however, it is noted for not being highly time-efficient. The single frame approach neglects the temporal dimension, omitting its consideration throughout the classification process. The methodology involves the extraction of a singular frame, denoted as f_k , from the entire video sequence, upon which the action identification is solely based. Given that the video is reduced to a single image, the classification process employs image-based mechanisms akin to traditional training classifiers such as Support Vector Machines [17], k-Nearest Neighbor [18], Bayesian models [19], or advanced deep learning techniques [20]. The selection of the frame f_k may occur through a straightforward process (e.g., $k = \text{rand}(1, n)$ or $k = \text{ceil}(n/2)$) or by adhering to intricate heuristics [21].

An alternative approach is presented in [15], where dense trajectories (DT) are extended to a multimodal context and applied to RGB-D data, incorporating depth-based and motion features. Scene flow is introduced as an additional input stream for a 2D CNN, alongside RGB and optical flow. Late fusion is employed across all modalities, and fine-tuning is conducted using pre-trained models on the UCF-101 dataset for RGB and optical flow streams. This method surpasses state-of-the-art approaches in terms of accuracy when evaluated on the MSRDailyActivity3D and Montalbano datasets [16]. In summary, existing Human Activity Recognition (HAR) methods tend to exhibit a trade-off between high accuracy and computational efficiency. Consequently, the goal of this paper is to devise a HAR system that concurrently achieves both accuracy and efficiency. The literature survey reveals the prevalent use of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) as a predominant mechanism for activity class detection. Additionally, the incorporation of multiple information streams, such as RGB, depth, and skeleton data, has proven instrumental in enhancing overall accuracy. The utility of transfer learning is evident in its ability to significantly reduce training time, while compression and fusion mechanisms exhibit promise in reducing video dimensionality from 3D to 2D, thereby enhancing efficiency in terms of both time and memory resources.

The fundamental concept underlying the proposed solution in this study revolves around the utilization of fusion mechanisms to simplify the problem of video classification typically addressed by 3D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) into a more tractable one—image classification resolvable with 2D CNNs. The 3D streams encompassing RGB, depth, and skeletal information are transformed into 2D representations through temporal fusion mechanisms. Subsequently, automated machine learning techniques are applied to these 2D representations, mitigating the challenges associated with training networks with large inputs and leveraging the current orientation of AutoML techniques towards image (rather than video) processing [16].

III. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1: Proposed diagram of the HAR method.

MULTI MODEL FUSION MECHANISM:

Temporal fusion mechanisms, while generally effective in analyzing motion induced by specific actions, encounter challenges in distinguishing between actions that share similar movement patterns. For instance, actions like throwing a ball and throwing a tossed paper rely on analogous motions, as do activities such as holding a laptop, a book, or a piece of paper. This inherent limitation can be addressed by incorporating information about surrounding objects into the classification model through the use of a context fusion mechanism. In the given example, if a ball is consistently identified in most frames of a video, the score for the class "throw ball" would be appropriately increased. Context fusion, in this context, involves the detection of scene objects by selecting a subset of frames and processing each through a 2D CNN trained for object detection. Consequently, each frame contributes a list of identified objects. The fusion mechanism's configuration can vary based on the desired importance attributed to context information. The fusion can be achieved either through reunion (an aggressive mechanism) or intersection (a lighter mechanism) of the object lists, depending on the desired emphasis on the contextual information, as illustrated in Figure 1. This approach effectively enhances the system's ability to differentiate between actions that share common motion characteristics by considering the contextual information provided by surrounding objects in the scene.

Fig 2: Process of Deriving the List of Surrounding Objects for Implementation of an Aggressive Context Fusion Mechanism.

Given a raw depth value $d[x][y]$, the cloud point p_{xyz} is obtained as follows:

$$p_{xyz} = d[x][y] \left[\frac{(x - C_x)}{f_x} \frac{(y - C_y)}{f_y} \ 1 \right] = [p_x \ p_y \ p_z]$$

where, f_x focal length in the direction of X-axis; f_y focal length in the direction of Y-axis; (c_x, c_y) center point of the depth camera.

Fig 3: Visualization of Depth Data Point Cloud from Various Angles

The term "skeleton images" in this context refers to a variant of Motion History Images (MHI), where the representation involves encoding the progression of time by diminishing the color intensity (i.e., darkening) of identified skeletal joints across successive video frames. The skeletal information is visually organized by visually clustering groups of joints that pertain to the same body part, each designated with a distinct color. This approach provides a visually interpretable representation of the temporal evolution of skeletal information in the context of human activity within the video sequence.

Projection maps are stored in binary format. For instance, the XOY projection map is:

$$proj_f [x][y] = \{1, 0, \exists pxy\}$$

Depth motion maps are computed for RGB data in a similar way to the MHIs. However, instead of applying the Hr function on an RGB image we are applying it to the three projection maps. In practice, DMMS are computed using the following formula:

$$dmm_v = \sum_{k=2}^{nr.frames} (map_v^k \neq map_v^{k-1}), v \in \{f, s, t\}$$

For simplicity, the size of the skeletal image is set to 100×100 . If a more accurate representation is required, such as capturing fine movements of the skeleton, the image size can be increased. Skeleton images offer the advantage of being highly customizable, allowing for the selection of joints to be considered and adjustment of algorithm constants, providing flexibility in tailoring the representation to specific needs.

IV. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The precision-recall trade-off curves for the Motion History Image (MHI)-based 2D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on the MSRDailyActivity3D dataset are presented, incorporating data augmentation. The notation "Precision@1" denotes the consideration of only the class with the highest score. The graphical representations include Precision versus Recall (left), Precision@1 versus the score threshold (middle), and recall@1 versus the score threshold (right). These curves provide insights into the model's performance characteristics, revealing the interplay between precision, recall, and score threshold for the specified classification task.

Fig 4: Motion History Image (MHI)-based 2D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on the MSRDailyActivity3D dataset

The Precision-recall trade-off curves for a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on the MSRDailyActivity3D dataset are depicted, highlighting the influence of data augmentation. The designation "Precision@1" indicates the consideration of solely the class with the highest score. The visual representations encompass Precision versus Recall (left) and Precision@1 (in red) and recall@1 (in blue) against the score threshold (right). These graphical depictions offer an analytical exploration of the model's performance characteristics, elucidating the intricate relationships between precision, recall, and the score threshold in the context of the specified classification task.

Fig 5: Precision-recall trade-off curves for a 3D Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on the MSRDailyActivity3D dataset

MSRDailyActivity3D: The correction of most misclassifications, such as "call cellphone," "drink," "play game," "read book," and "use laptop," is achieved through the context fusion mechanism, leveraging object detection to identify relevant items (cellphone, bottle, game console, book, laptop). Errors in classifying "stand up" and "sit down" are rectified by the channel fusion mechanism, amalgamating information from all five Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). An unresolved challenge involves distinguishing between "read book" and "write on a paper," primarily due to the similarity in motion patterns and difficulty in accurately identifying objects, often hindered by inconvenient positions. UTD-MHAD: Depth and skeleton information prove instrumental in distinguishing activities with similar motion patterns, such as "bowling" and "lunge," or "swipe left" and "swipe right." Given the absence of objects in actions performed in this dataset, the context fusion mechanism does not significantly influence system accuracy. A confusion matrix, displayed in Fig. 4 in Appendix A, highlights classes that are challenging to differentiate, predominantly characterized by analogous movement patterns and body postures. NTU RGB+D: Difficulties in distinguishing certain actions arise from either nearly identical motion patterns or filming from a considerable distance, rendering the context fusion mechanism less effective. For instance, limitations in object detection, using YOLOv3, become apparent in detecting a toothbrush in the "brush teeth" class when the person is too far from the camera. PRECIS HAR: The incorporation of channel and context fusion mechanisms yields a notable accuracy increase, elevating performance from 85.63% to 94.38%. The context fusion mechanism proves particularly impactful, aiding in distinguishing actions like "drink from a bottle" and "drink from a mug" (refer to Fig. 5), as well as discerning activities involving object interaction from those without objects. The overall improvement underscores the significance of the context fusion mechanism in refining classification outcomes.

Additionally, our experimentation substantiates the significance of each distinct information stream, namely RGB, depth, skeleton images, and a list containing surrounding objects. These diverse streams contribute uniquely to the identification of human actions. Our observations indicate the following:

1. MHI-based CNN Performance: Motion History Image-based CNNs excel in identifying dynamic activities such as walking, waving, cheering, and clapping hands, particularly in well-lit conditions. (using MMFM)
2. DMM-based CNN Capabilities: CNNs utilizing Depth Motion Maps (DMM) prove effective in identifying activities occurring in challenging lighting conditions or even in the absence of adequate lighting, such as falling from the bed, sleepwalking, and fainting. They also demonstrate utility in activities that necessitate viewpoints beyond the front view, such as reading a book or sitting still. (using MMFM)
3. Role of Skeleton Image-based CNN: CNNs processing skeleton images contribute to the identification of dynamic activities and sometimes serve as corrections for Motion History Images (MHIs). However, their trust coefficient is relatively low. They prove beneficial in recognizing actions with similar motion curves executed using different body parts, for instance, raising one hand or one leg. (using MMFM) In summary, each information stream plays a distinctive role, and their combined integration enhances the system's ability to accurately identify a diverse array of human activities, accounting for varying conditions and nuances in the execution of actions.

V. CONCLUSION

The paper presents an innovative framework for human activity recognition in indoor settings, leveraging fusion mechanisms and automated machine learning. The framework integrates information from all channels of a 3D video, including RGB, depth, skeleton, and context objects, utilizing time, channel, and context fusion mechanisms. Each type of information undergoes analysis through dedicated 2D convolutional neural networks (CNNs), implemented using Google's AutoML tool. The final output is obtained by combining the outputs of all these specialized networks. The achieved high accuracies with the Motion History Image-based Convolutional Neural Networks (MHI-CNNs) validate the efficiency of compressing a video into an image using a pixel-fusion mechanism. Furthermore, the study demonstrates the effectiveness of multiple predictions, affirming that training several CNNs individually and combining their results leads to significantly improved classification accuracy. This approach contributes to the optimization of human activity recognition systems by capitalizing on fusion mechanisms, automated machine learning, and the advantageous properties of pixel-level fusion in video-to-image compression. Based on our conducted experiments, the presented framework has demonstrated attributes of being expeditiously trainable, owing to the incorporation of AutoML, and exhibits a high level of accuracy. Its highly customizable nature is evidenced by the ease with which modules, about temporal,

channel, or context fusion, can be added or removed and subsequently trained. Furthermore, the introduction of a new RGB-D dataset in this study is expected to contribute significantly to the computer vision community, fostering the development of novel methods for human activity recognition. This dataset provides an opportunity for researchers to explore and advance the field. In the trajectory of future work, we intend to scale the training and testing of the proposed method to encompass large-scale datasets. Currently, the system can detect a limited number of activity classes, some of which are designed for scientific exploration rather than representing the daily activities of older individuals. To address this, the system will be trained on a broader spectrum of activities that are more representative of the daily routines of the elderly population. This integration holds promise for combining surveillance capabilities with assertive functionalities. The envisioned scenario involves the robot monitoring individuals while also assisting with household chores. This integration aligns with the broader objective of leveraging technology to enhance the well-being and support of individuals in their daily lives, particularly in the context of an aging population.

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